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EFFECTIVE

PROTECTION AND RESTORATION MANAGEMENT · MEDITERRANEAN MPAs

**Enhancing social well being and economic prosperity
by reinforcing the eFFECTIVENess of protection and
restoration management in Mediterranean MPAs**

Deliverable 9.3

Communication and Dissemination
Activities Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, D9.3 – Communication and Dissemination Activities Report, provides a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination efforts conducted by the EFFECTIVE project from Month 1 (June 2023) to Month 17 (October 2024). The main objective of this report is to demonstrate the various activities undertaken to promote the project's objectives, disseminate its findings, and engage with relevant stakeholders across different channels.

This deliverable builds upon the foundation laid out in D9.1 – Plan for Dissemination, Communication, and Stakeholder Engagement, submitted in November 2023. While D9.1 focused on presenting a strategic plan for the entire project duration, including the tools, channels, and methodologies to be used, D9.3 shifts the focus towards the implementation and outcomes of these planned activities. It highlights the progress made, key results achieved, and the effectiveness of the strategies executed so far.

The Dissemination Plan outlined in D9.1 emphasised the structured sharing of project results with the public, while the Communication Plan aimed to increase visibility and raise awareness about EFFECTIVE among broader audiences. The Stakeholder Engagement Plan identified key groups, detailing targeted outreach strategies and engagement activities to maximize impact. In this deliverable, we provide a detailed account of how these plans were put into action, including the adaptations made in response to evolving project needs and external factors.

D9.3 aims to serve as a dynamic record of the EFFECTIVE project's communication and dissemination journey, capturing the efforts made to reach diverse audiences, share impactful results, and foster stakeholder collaboration. It also lays the groundwork for future activities by analyzing the effectiveness of past efforts, offering insights to refine our strategies moving forward.

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EBMS	Ecosystem-Based Management System
EU	European Union
M	Month
MPAs	Marine Protected Areas
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1. Introduction

The EFFECTIVE project aims to restore and protect the EU's Mediterranean Blue Natural Capital by developing a standardized Ecosystem-Based Management System (EBMS) that integrates Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). To achieve these ambitious objectives, effective communication and dissemination play a critical role in raising awareness, sharing knowledge, and engaging stakeholders across diverse sectors.

Deliverable 9.1, submitted in November 2023, laid the groundwork for the project's communication and dissemination efforts by presenting a comprehensive Plan for Dissemination, Communication, and Stakeholder Engagement. This plan defined the strategies, tools, and channels to be employed throughout the project to ensure consistent messaging and effective outreach. It emphasized the importance of differentiating between dissemination, focused on sharing project results with specific audiences, and communication, aimed at promoting project activities to a broader audience. The plan also outlined targeted stakeholder engagement strategies to maximize the impact and uptake of project outcomes.

Building on this framework, the current deliverable, D9.3, focuses on the implementation of these strategies from Month 1 (June 2023) to Month 17 (October 2024). It highlights the communication channels used, such as social media, newsletters, events, and scientific publications, and provides an overview of the activities carried out to enhance the visibility of the project and engage key stakeholders. The report serves as a record of progress made and lessons learned, demonstrating how EFFECTIVE has successfully promoted its vision and fostered stakeholder involvement through ongoing and adaptive communication efforts.

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The communication and dissemination strategy of the EFFECTIVE project, as outlined in Deliverable D9.1 and updated in D9.2 (due in November 2024), aims to efficiently raise awareness, disseminate results, and promote the exploitation of project outcomes across various stakeholders. This approach is crucial for maximizing the project's impact and fostering the uptake of its results beyond the project's lifespan.

2.1 Goals and Objectives

The strategy is structured into three distinct levels, each addressing different stages and types of engagement:

1. **Raising Awareness:** This initial stage focuses on informing relevant stakeholders about the existence, scope, and objectives of the EFFECTIVE project. The goal is to create a foundational understanding among target audiences, paving the way for deeper engagement as the project progresses.
2. **Strategic Dissemination:** At this stage, the aim is to share the results of the project with a broader audience, including policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the academic community. This involves presenting research findings, innovative solutions, and project achievements to inform stakeholders about the progress and benefits of the project.
3. **Exploitation:** The final level of the strategy focuses on promoting the use and adoption of project outcomes. This involves engaging with end users, industry players, and decision-makers to ensure that the innovations and knowledge generated by EFFECTIVE are effectively utilized in practice, enhancing the sustainability of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

2.2 Target Audiences

The EFFECTIVE strategy targets a diverse range of stakeholders, clustered into specific groups to tailor communication efforts effectively:

Audience category	Target Audience	Type of information/material	Channels/tools	Objective communication	KPIs
Governance	MPA/regional authorities	Summary reports and roadmaps	Dedicated meetings with workshops, and roundtables	Promotion of EBMS implementation and sustainable MPA Management	>50 policy makers
	Port authorities	Technical and summary reports	Dedicated meeting with workshops	Promotion of sustainable maritime transports and footprint reduction	>20 ports

Main Industry	Fisheries & Aquaculture	Summary reports for awareness	Workshop and journals	Increase knowledge about MPAs benefits for biodiversity and fish stocks	>100
	Ecotourism sector	Summary reports for awareness	Workshop and journals	Increase knowledge about MPAs benefits for biodiversity and fish stocks	>100 entrepreneurs
	Offshore-Energy	Summary reports for awareness	Workshop and journals	Promote the use of NbS in offshore structures	>30 companies
Scientific community	Scientific researchers (EBM)	Papers or proceedings	Scientific journal, congress and/or roundtables	Increase EBMS knowledge and application	>1000 researchers
	Marine technology researchers (restoration solutions)	Papers, proceeding or reports	Scientific journal, congress and/or roundtables	Increase visibility on the environmental improvement impact of nature-based restoration technologies	>500 researchers
Citizens	Local communities	Flyer and reports	Workshops and seminars	Inform about the project results and implementation	>500
	Tour Operators	Flyer and reports	Workshops and seminars	Promote the local business in the area	>50 tourist operators

	Online citizens	Website & participation Hub	Internet, Search Engines, social media	Increase reach and level of public engagement, create learning effects and knowledge building in local communities	>65.000 citizen observations
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Table 1: Target Audience and Objectives for the EFFECTIVE project

2.3 Key Messages

The EFFECTIVE communication and dissemination efforts are designed around key messages and themes that resonate with its diverse audiences:

1. Sustainability and Marine Conservation:

- Highlight the project's contribution to the conservation and restoration of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), emphasizing the importance of sustainable practices and their long-term benefits for marine ecosystems.

2. Innovation and Research Excellence:

- Promote the innovative approaches and cutting-edge research methods employed in EFFECTIVE, showcasing advancements in ecosystem-based management (EBM) and marine restoration technologies.

3. Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement:

- Emphasize the collaborative nature of the project, showcasing the involvement of various stakeholders, including industry partners, researchers, and local communities, in achieving shared goals for marine conservation. All information and details will be covered in the Deliverable 9.6 Liaising activities and growth of the International Stakeholder Community report (due in November 2024).

4. Policy Impact and Adoption:

- Communicate the relevance of EFFECTIVE's findings to policymakers and encourage the integration of project recommendations into local, national, and EU-level marine policies.

5. Gender-Inclusive and Accessible Communication:

- Maintain a focus on inclusivity, using gender-neutral language and accessible communication methods to reach a broad audience and ensure that project information is easily understandable.

2.4 Approach

The EFFECTIVE strategy employs a multi-channel, individualized approach to ensure maximum reach and impact:

- **Digital Channels:** Utilizes the project website, social media platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and X/Twitter), newsletters, and webinars to engage with a global audience.
- **Events and Conferences:** Actively participates in scientific conferences, industry events, workshops, and stakeholder meetings to present project results and foster direct interactions with key stakeholders.
- **Visual Identity:** A cohesive visual identity is maintained across all communication materials to ensure brand recognition and strengthen the project's visibility, as presented in the D9.1 Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan (delivered in November 2023).

This strategic framework ensures that communication efforts are aligned with the project's objectives, targeting the right audiences with relevant messages at the right time. By building long-term relationships and leveraging the expertise of its partners, EFFECTIVE aims to foster a sustainable impact in marine conservation and enhance the visibility of its results on both local and international levels.

3. Communication Activities Overview

From M1 (June 2023) to M17 (October 2024), the EFFECTIVE project implemented a comprehensive communications and dissemination strategy to raise awareness, engage stakeholders, and showcase project developments. The activities were carefully designed to reach diverse target audiences, including project partners, stakeholders in the marine ecosystem sector, policymakers, and the general public. This overview provides a detailed account of the key activities carried out during this period.

3.1 Social Media Campaigns

EFFECTIVE's social media strategy has been pivotal in building a strong online presence and fostering community engagement. The project leveraged multiple platforms, including LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook and X/Twitter, to disseminate information and updates regularly. Some of the prominent social media campaigns include:

- **Kick-Off Meeting (June 2023)**

This campaign marked the official launch of the project, with an article¹ on the project website, as well as posts on LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and X/Twitter highlighting the consortium's formation and goals.

Figure 1: EFFECTIVE Kick-Off Meeting (group photo)

- **Meet Our Partners Campaign (November 2023 - September 2024)**

A dedicated series aimed at introducing each project partner, showcasing their expertise, and detailing their roles within EFFECTIVE. This campaign included detailed articles and social media posts featuring partners like CTN, Ocean Ecostructures, and CMMI, among others.

¹ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/06/15/effective-kick-off-meeting-igniting-the-effective-projects-wave-of-innovation/>

Figure 2: Meet our Partner CTN (example)

- **Benefits for Stakeholders Campaign (June 2024 - ongoing)**

Focused on demonstrating the advantages EFFECTIVE brings to different stakeholder groups, this ongoing campaign features targeted posts addressing Blue Economy companies, marine scientists, fisheries, policymakers, and citizens.

Figure 3: Benefits for Blue Economy Companies Visual (example)

3.2 Blog Posts and Articles

Throughout the reporting period, the EFFECTIVE project published several blog posts and articles to provide in-depth insights into project milestones, research developments, and collaborative efforts. Key highlights include:

- **Partner Collaboration Articles**

These articles showcased unique contributions from partners, such as HCMR's underwater surveys in the Eastern Mediterranean² and Ocean Ecostructures' creation of a biomaterial for marine ecosystem regeneration³.

- **Educational Content**

A series of informative posts and articles explained complex topics, such as the concept of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)⁴, Ecosystem-Based Management Systems (EBMS)⁵, and the use of Digital Twins in marine research⁶.

3.3 Press Releases

As part of the EFFECTIVE project's dissemination strategy, a press release was issued on October 19th, 2023, marking a significant milestone in introducing the project to a broad audience, including industry stakeholders, scientific communities, policymakers, and the general public. The press release served as an official announcement of the project's launch, its goals, and the collaborative effort of its partners. The primary objective of the press release was to raise awareness about the EFFECTIVE Project and highlight its mission to enhance the protection and restoration of Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

Figure 4: EFFECTIVE Project 1st Press Release (October 2023)

² <https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/11/15/hcmrs-underwater-surveys-in-the-eastern-mediterranean/>

³ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/11/15/ocean-ecostructures-creates-a-biomaterial-to-regenerate-marine-ecosystems/>

⁴ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/02/15/understanding-marine-protected-areas/>

⁵ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/05/29/exploring-ecosystem-based-management-systems-ebms/>

⁶ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/05/21/understanding-the-concept-of-a-digital-twin/>

3.4 Newsletters

To keep stakeholders informed about project developments and upcoming events, EFFECTIVE launched two editions of its newsletter. These newsletters provided a comprehensive overview of recent activities, partner highlights, and featured articles on ongoing research. The newsletters were distributed via email (through the project's MailChimp account, managed by the partner Impact2Day) and promoted on social media platforms, encouraging subscriptions to expand outreach.

- 1st Edition⁷ released in **February 2024**
- 2nd Edition⁸ released in **July 2024**

Figure 5: EFFECTIVE Newsletter (example)

3.5 Events

Internal Online Workshops

EFFECTIVE organised and participated in two different workshops, focusing on knowledge exchange and stakeholder engagement:

- **Internal Citizen Science Workshop⁹ (January 2024):** This workshop brought together project partners and external experts to discuss the integration of citizen science in EFFECTIVE's monitoring efforts. The online meeting facilitated the sharing of best practices and explored ways to enhance public engagement in marine ecosystem restoration activities.

⁷ <https://mailchi.mp/aaa83271563b/effective-project-newsletter-1>

⁸ <https://mailchi.mp/a5c6e6af1cff/effective-project-newsletter-12700324>

⁹ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/01/24/exploring-the-possibilities-of-citizen-science-effective-citizen-science-workshop-2024/>

Figure 6: Citizen Science Workshop attendees

- Stakeholder Identification Internal Workshop (May 2024):** The goal of this online workshop was simple and very interactive between project partners. Divided into two virtual rooms, project partners had to brainstorm on the most important benefits and advantages for the stakeholders' groups already identified within the EFFECTIVE project. There are 13 different groups of stakeholders identified (as detailed in D9.1, D9.2 and D9.6). This workshop helped build a foundation for the creation of the "Benefits for Stakeholders" social media campaign, already presented above in this document.

Industry Events

The EFFECTIVE project team actively participated in several industry events, both online and in-person, to enhance visibility and foster networking opportunities. Key events include:

- Breaking the Surface Workshop (September 2023):** A marine science workshop where the project was showcased to a specialized audience of 200 researchers and industry experts.

Figure 7: Breaking the Surface Workshop

- **Ocean Data Week – the Ocean Race (June 2023):** a conference aimed to an audience of 60 citizens and general public in which, during the panel "Between biodiversity and sustainability: science to raise awareness, awareness to guide behaviour", Noelia Ortega, the Project Coordinator, introduced EFFECTIVE and the main project goals.
- **Baltic Sea Science Congress 2023¹⁰ (August 2023):** IOW partner delivered a presentation about the EFFECTIVE project, focusing on an ecosystem services assessment for a nature-based coastal protection measure.
- **Festival della Scienza¹¹ (November 2023):** the EFFECTIVE partner Francesco Misurale talked about ETT's work and experience concerning ocean data collection, also mentioning its contribution in the project EFFECTIVE.
- **Smart City Expo World Congress (December 2023):** Participation in this global initiative, through the side event titled "Tomorrow. Blue Economy", provided an opportunity to discuss the project's role in enhancing marine ecosystem management through digital innovations.

Figure 8: Tomorrow. Blue Economy - the side event of Smart City Expo World Congress

- **I Summit on Nature-Based Solutions for the Blue Economy¹² (February 2024):** The project presented its approach and early findings, engaging with stakeholders interested in sustainable marine solutions.

¹⁰ <https://www.syke.fi/projects/bssc2023>

¹¹ <https://www.festivalscienza.it/>

¹² https://ctnaval.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Wrap-Up.pdf?utm_source=Dynamics%20365%20Customer%20Insights%20-%20Journeys&utm_medium=email&utm_term=N%2FA&utm_campaign=SN%3A%20Agradecimiento%20Summit%20-%20Env%20C3%ADo%20f14693&utm_content=Agradecimiento%20Summit%20-%20Env%20C3%ADo%20presentaciones%20Extranjeros#msdynmkt_trackingcontext=9a2002b6-7b8a-4590-a4f3-a28e7dae623d

Figure 9: I Summit on Nature-Based Solutions for the Blue Economy

- **European Ocean Days (April 2024):** A matchmaking event, where the coordinator CTN delivered a presentation of the EFFECTIVE project in order to inform stakeholders and make relevant contacts.
- **MARTECH – 11th International Workshop on Marine Technology¹³ (June 2024):** Valeria Pizziol, from ETT, gave a brief presentation of the project EFFECTIVE on the Session 5.2 about “Robotics, Artificial Intelligence, Sensors and Communications”.
- **St. Paul's school marine conservation & restoration workshop (June 2024):** An education and training event led by Ocean Ecostructures (OE), aimed to citizens, educators, students and general public. OE's scientific team went to St. Paul's School to do different workshops with the students, teaching them about the monitoring tool of the EFFECTIVE project, species identification, corals replantation and also a presentation talking about EFFECTIVE and OE's restoration actions within the project.
- **2nd EU Blue Parks Community Workshop – Effective management of marine protected areas (July 2024):** Presentation of the EFFECTIVE project (led by CTN) in order to inform stakeholders and make relevant contacts.
- **Littoral 24 – European Coastal Challenge Summit¹⁴ (September 2024):** The partner IOW participated in the 17th edition of this conference, by having a presentation on "Assessing habitat and ecosystem service changes in shallow eutrophic coastal waters using remote imagery", related to their WP3.

¹³ <https://martech-workshop.org/documents/Programme%20Martech24.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://littoral24.univ-ovidius.ro/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Littoral24-Program-1.pdf>

3.6 Key Activities by Project Partners

In addition to the central communication efforts carried out by the WP 9 leaders of the EFFECTIVE project, several other project partners actively contributed to promoting the initiative through their own communication channels. These activities, reported through an excel file that is hosted in the project's online repository, go from social media posts and website articles to interviews and participation in media stories, having significantly enhanced the project's visibility and outreach. The involvement of partners in these efforts has helped to disseminate project information to a broader and more diverse audience, engaging both specialized stakeholders and the general public.

Coral Soul

- On July 7, 2023, Coral Soul shared an Instagram post¹⁵ introducing the EFFECTIVE project, reaching 133 engaged users.
- A follow-up Instagram Reel¹⁶ on July 9, 2023, showcased the first expedition in Sardinia, highlighting coral restoration efforts as part of the project. The reel gained 352 likes, engaging the general public with visual content on marine conservation.
- On September 28, 2023, Coral Soul participated in a radio interview¹⁷ for the program "Españoles en la Mar" of RTVE, where the EFFECTIVE project was discussed, bringing it to a wider audience through traditional media channels.

ETT

- ETT actively promoted its involvement in the project through multiple posts across Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram. On February 27, 2024, they shared content¹⁸ about their participation in the 2nd Consortium Meeting and the I Summit on Nature-Based Solutions for the Blue Economy¹⁹.
- In March 2024, ETT published on LinkedIn²⁰ and Facebook²¹ regarding the approval by the European Parliament of the "Nature Restoration Law" which recognizes the importance of mitigation actions such as "restoration" to reduce the effects of global warming of the seas within the safety threshold of +1.5°C, referring to the EFFECTIVE project.

¹⁵ https://www.instagram.com/p/CuZvIaLtyn7/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link

¹⁶ https://www.instagram.com/reel/CufNXqbg5H9/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link

¹⁷ <https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/espanoles-en-la-mar/conferencia-anual-sobre-transporte-maritimo/6979819/>

¹⁸ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ett-spa_ett-ett-ett-activity-7168981032627638272-VBZK?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

¹⁹ <https://ettsolutions.com/en/effective-events-february-2024/>

²⁰ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ett-spa_so-ocean-physics-activity-7173328151320608768-CrZl?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

²¹

<https://www.facebook.com/ettspa/posts/pfbid02uVUwcb3o9hJAqHXpfxAawDmJUVbFUXheCZSSCi4KCgos5yeWqdV3GcKwCCcNLwZhI>

- ETT continued its efforts with a website update²² on June 2, 2024, where they mentioned the EFFECTIVE project in the context of their presentation at the Martech 2024 conference.

UkrSCES

- The Ukrainian Scientific Centre of Ecology of the Sea (UkrSCES) published multiple articles on their website about their participation in project activities, such as the kick-off meeting²³ (June 16, 2023), the EFFECTIVE workshop on Citizen Science²⁴ (January 17, 2024), the 2nd Consortium Meeting²⁵ (March 4, 2024) and about the project's participation in the I Summit on Nature-Oriented Solutions for the Blue Economy²⁶ (March 11, 2024).
- Their consistent updates provided visibility to the project among the scientific community and broader audiences interested in environmental conservation.

SPOTTERON

- In August 2024, SPOTTERON launched the first version of the Participation Hub website (www.cosea.app), creating a digital platform for public engagement. This initiative helped amplify the project's outreach efforts and facilitated citizen participation.

FORTH

- The Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH) took part in an interview²⁷ with a Greek online newspaper, where they explained their role in the EFFECTIVE project. The interview provided a detailed overview of the project's objectives and FORTH's contributions, reaching a Greek-speaking audience.

CMMI

- The Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute (CMMI) was featured in several high-profile media stories, including an article by the Associated French Press²⁸ (May 17, 2024) on floating nurseries for coral restoration. This story was picked up by various international media outlets, significantly increasing the project's visibility on a global scale.
- CMMI also participated in interviews with prominent TV channels, such as France 3 for their 'Mediterraneo' series (which will come out in February 2025) and Cyprus

²² <https://ettsolutions.com/paper-ett-martech-2024/>

²³ https://sea.gov.ua/index.php/2023/06/16/effective_project_start/

²⁴ https://sea.gov.ua/index.php/2024/01/17/effective_workshop_science_2024/

²⁵ https://sea.gov.ua/index.php/2024/03/04/effective_mursiya_consortium/

²⁶ https://sea.gov.ua/index.php/2024/03/11/blue_economy_summit_1st/

²⁷ <https://www.amna.gr/eu/article/823975/Europaiko-ergo-me-ti-summetochi-tou-ITE--gia-tin-prostasia-ton-thalassion-prostateuomenon-periochon-tis-Mesogeiou--apo-tin-klimatiki-krisi>

²⁸ <https://www.france24.com/en/live-news/20240717-cyprus-pioneers-coral-conservation-project-in-the-med>

Public TV 'RIK1' (which will be live in the upcoming months), focusing on their innovative coral conservation efforts under the EFFECTIVE project.

The partner-led communication activities have proven to be instrumental in reaching new audiences and enhancing the project's impact. By leveraging their own networks and platforms, the partners have been able to tap into various stakeholder groups, including local communities, marine conservation enthusiasts, and scientific experts. This collaborative dissemination approach has not only amplified the project's message but also contributed to building a strong, engaged community around EFFECTIVE's objectives and activities.

4. Dissemination Activities Overview

During the reporting period from M1 (June 2023) to M17 (October 2024), the EFFECTIVE project engaged in a variety of dissemination activities aimed at sharing scientific knowledge, project developments, and research findings with the broader marine science community, industry stakeholders, and policymakers. These efforts were strategically implemented to ensure the visibility of the project within relevant scientific and professional circles and to foster collaboration. The following is a detailed account of these activities.

4.1 Scientific Publications

One of the core elements of EFFECTIVE's dissemination strategy has been the publication of scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals. These publications have played a critical role in sharing the project's findings with the academic community, contributing to the knowledge base on marine ecosystem management and restoration. Notable publications include:

- **Perspectives and Scenarios for Coastal Fisheries in a Social-Ecological Context: An Ecosystem Service Assessment Approach in the German Baltic Sea²⁹:** a paper co-authored by project partners, focusing on innovative methodologies for monitoring marine ecosystems. This publication contributed to the broader scientific discourse on marine protected areas and their role in ecosystem conservation.

4.2 Conference Presentations

EFFECTIVE actively participated in various international and regional conferences, where project representatives presented key findings, methodologies, and technological innovations. These events provided a platform for networking, knowledge exchange, and engaging with stakeholders from academia, industry, and policymaking. Highlights include:

- **I Summit on Nature-Based Solutions for the Blue Economy³⁰ (February 2024):** The project team delivered multiple presentations showcasing EFFECTIVE's approaches to ecosystem restoration, discussing the potential of nature-based solutions for enhancing the resilience of marine habitats.
- **Horizon Europe Mission Ocean Work Programme³¹ (April 2024):** A key opportunity to present the project's application of digital twins in marine monitoring and its alignment with the objectives of the EU Mission Ocean and Waters.
- **EURESFO 2024³² (June 2024):** EFFECTIVE's participation in this conference included several presentations by project partners, focusing on pilot studies, data-driven monitoring techniques, and the integration of citizen science in marine research.

²⁹ <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/22/15732>

³⁰ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/04/08/unveiling-insights-from-the-i-summit-on-nature-based-solutions-for-the-blue-economy/>

³¹ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/04/03/effective-project-showcased-at-eu-research-innovation-session-horizon-europe-mission-ocean-work-programme/>

³² <https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/08/12/euresfo-2024-recap-advancing-urban-resilience/>

4.3 Collaborations and Partner Contributions

EFFECTIVE has actively collaborated with project partners and external stakeholders to amplify its scientific dissemination efforts. Key examples include:

- **Underwater Surveys by HCMR³³ (August 2023):** The EFFECTIVE partner Hellenic Centre for Marine Research conducted detailed underwater surveys in the Eastern Mediterranean as part of a collaborative effort to map and assess marine ecosystems. The findings from these surveys were shared through conference presentations, internal reports and even on European Sting³⁴ (external online newspaper).
- **Digital Twins of the Ocean - Partner Workshop (March 2024):** A workshop organised by ILIAD and promoted within EFFECTIVE social media channels, exploring the use of digital twins as a tool for policymakers and researchers. This event focused on demonstrating the capabilities of digital twins in simulating marine environments and assessing the impact of conservation measures.

4.4 Dissemination through Media and Public Engagement

Beyond traditional academic channels, EFFECTIVE expanded its reach through media engagements and public dissemination efforts:

- **Euronews Documentary Feature³⁵ (August 2024):** The project was featured in Euronews' "Ocean" documentary series, providing a broad audience with insights into its goals, pilot activities, and the potential impact on marine ecosystem restoration.
- **Public Awareness Articles and Social Media Engagement:** The dissemination strategy included publishing accessible articles on marine conservation topics and promoting them via social media channels to raise awareness among non-expert audiences. Topics ranged from explaining ecosystem-based management systems to the benefits of marine protected areas.

³³ <https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/11/15/hcmrs-underwater-surveys-in-the-eastern-mediterranean/>

³⁴ https://europeansting.com/2023/07/03/eu-mission-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-e106-million-for-18-new-projects-for-protection-conservation-depollution-and-innovation/?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAR3VVgXiCiIN_otL5TCoxOjKe2LZQbGCuQ3E1hcjn-52uaYQ3YrcDVV0dc_aem_vDA3wctpjz1bkcr3ZxpyA

³⁵ <https://www.euronews.com/green/2024/08/27/marine-heatwaves-spreading-like-wildfires-warn-experts>

Figure 10: Public Awareness Article example (shared on EFFECTIVE Website and Social Media Channels)

The EFFECTIVE project's dissemination activities have successfully engaged the scientific community, industry stakeholders, and the general public, sharing insights and fostering discussions around innovative approaches to marine ecosystem monitoring and restoration. Through publications, conference presentations, workshops, and media features, the project has significantly contributed to advancing knowledge and promoting best practices in the field of marine science. The following sections will provide detailed analyses of specific activities, including their objectives, methodologies, target audiences, and key performance indicators (KPIs) where relevant.

5. Key Results and Impact Analysis

This section presents an in-depth analysis of the communications and dissemination activities carried out during the first 17 months of the EFFECTIVE project, focusing on metrics and insights that reflect the reach, engagement, and overall effectiveness of our efforts. By evaluating key performance indicators (KPIs) such as social media followers gained, newsletter open rates, and media coverage, we aim to measure the success of our initiatives and their contribution to the project's visibility.

Through strategic social media campaigns, press releases, newsletters, and participation in key events, we targeted a diverse range of stakeholders, including marine scientists, policymakers, industry players, and the general public. This analysis explores the tangible impact of these activities, detailing how specific campaigns have:

- **Enhanced Project Awareness:** By leveraging multi-channel dissemination strategies, we successfully raised awareness about the project's objectives, methodologies, and milestones, reaching a broad audience within the Mediterranean conservation landscape.
- **Increased Stakeholder Engagement:** Targeted campaigns, such as the "Meet Our Partners" and "Benefits for Stakeholders", played a critical role in fostering engagement among key stakeholders, building a community around the project's goals.
- **Boosted Online Presence:** Analysing growth in our social media following and engagement rates, as well as improvements in website traffic and newsletter subscriber numbers, provides insight into the project's expanding digital footprint.

This section will highlight the most effective activities, detailing the key results achieved, demonstrating how our communication efforts have laid a strong foundation for ongoing stakeholder engagement and knowledge dissemination in the project's next phases.

5.1 Key Performance Indicators for Communication and Dissemination Activities

To effectively measure the impact of the communication and dissemination efforts of the EFFECTIVE project, a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was established as part of Work Package 9. These KPIs provide a quantitative and qualitative framework to evaluate the success of various activities, including social media engagement, website traffic, event participation, and media outreach. The base strategy for these activities was thoroughly analysed in Deliverable 9.1 and will continue to be refined and detailed in Deliverable 9.2, also due in November 2024. By monitoring these metrics, the project team has been able to assess the reach, engagement, and overall effectiveness of their strategies, ensuring alignment with the project's goals of raising awareness, fostering stakeholder engagement, and disseminating knowledge about marine conservation and restoration efforts in the Mediterranean region.

Category	Sub-Category	Activity Name	Description	Communication Channels	Outcome (KPI)	Evidence (URL)
Social Media Campaign	Project Consortium Meetings	Kick-Off Meeting of the EFFECTIVE Project	On June 13-14, 2023, the EFFECTIVE Project has kicked off in Brussels.	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 22 views Instagram = 12 likes Twitter = 317 views; 6 likes; 2 re-tweets Facebook = 2 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/06/15/effective-kick-off-meeting-igniting-the-effective-projects-wave-of-innovation/
		2 nd Consortium Meeting of the EFFECTIVE Project	On February 27, 2024, the consortium of the EFFECTIVE project gathered in Murcia, Spain.	1 Website article 2 LinkedIn posts 2 Instagram posts 2 Twitter posts 2 Facebook posts	Website = 11 views LinkedIn = 46 & 54 reactions; 2 comments; 8 & 8 shares Instagram = 10 likes & 12 likes; 1 comment Twitter posts = 32 & 169 views; 3 likes & 4 likes; 3 re-tweets Facebook posts = 3 & 2 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/04/02/reflecting-on-progress-effective-project-consortium-meeting-in-murcia/
	Meet our Partners Campaign	Presenting CTN		1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 135 views LinkedIn = 63 reactions; 1 comment; 11 shares Instagram = 25 likes & 1 comment Twitter = 93 views; 5 likes; 1 re-tweet Facebook = 3 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/11/08/meet-our-partners-ctn-coordinating-a-sustainable-future-for-mediterranean-marine-ecosystems/
		Presenting Ocean Ecostructures		1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 59 views LinkedIn = 51 reactions; 9 shares Instagram = 15 likes Twitter = 43 views; 2 likes; 1 re-tweet Facebook = 4 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/12/05/meet-our-partners-ocean-ecostructures-the-catalysts-of-marine-regeneration-in-the-effective-project/

	Presenting CMMI	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 33 views LinkedIn = 62 reactions; 4 shares Instagram = 9 likes Twitter = 37 views; 4 likes Facebook = 4 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/01/10/meet-effective-partners-the-cyprus-marine-and-maritime-institute-cmmi/
	Presenting MARIS	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post	Website = 26 views LinkedIn = 39 reactions; 3 shares Instagram = 6 likes Twitter = 34 views; 7 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/01/29/meet-our-partners-maris-the-marine-data-management-pillar-for-the-effective-project/
	Presenting F6S	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post	Website = 13 views LinkedIn = 50 reactions; 7 shares Instagram = 4 likes Twitter = 29 views; 2 likes; 1 re-tweet	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/02/21/meet-our-partners-f6s-is-the-communication-dissemination-leader-of-effective/
	Presenting SPOTTERON	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 10 views LinkedIn = 16 reactions; 2 shares Instagram = 4 likes Facebook = 1 like	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/03/08/spotteron-empowers-citizen-science-in-the-effective-project/
	Presenting Coral Soul	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 36 views LinkedIn = 29 reactions; 1 comment; 1 share Instagram = 10 likes Facebook = 1 like	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/04/19/coral-soul-the-partner-responsible-for-deep-coral-reef-restoration-in-the-effective-project/
	Presenting ETT	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post	Website = 21 views LinkedIn = 26 reactions; 3 shares	Link to website article: https://effective-

		1 Instagram post	Instagram = 6 likes	euproject.eu/2024/06/05/meet-our-partners-ett/
	Presenting DHI	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post	Website = 15 views LinkedIn = 90 reactions; 1 comment; 2 shares Instagram = 4 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/07/03/meet-our-partners-dhi/
	Presenting IOW	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post	Website = 10 views LinkedIn = 6 reactions Instagram = 4 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/07/10/meet-our-partner-iow/
	Presenting Seastainable Ventures	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 6 views LinkedIn = 26 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 5 likes Facebook = 1 like	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/08/27/meet-our-partners-seastainable-ventures/
	Presenting Eurecat	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 46 reactions; 6 shares Instagram = 8 likes Twitter = 22 views; 1 like Facebook = 1 like	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7239952791643844609
	Presenting Marine Forest Team	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 19 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 20 likes Twitter = 24 views; 1 like Facebook = 0 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7244974308576444416
Festivities Celebration Campaigns	Mediterranean Coast Day	1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Instagram = 10 likes Twitter = 314 views; 8 likes; 2 reposts Facebook = 4 likes; 2 shares	Link to Instagram post: https://www.instagram.com/p/CzBeBunt5li/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==
	Mediterranean Day Celebration	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post	LinkedIn = 38 reactions; 4 shares Instagram = 7 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/u

			1 Facebook post	Facebook = 4 likes; 1 share	pdate/urn:li:activity:7135211172831580161
		Happy Holidays	1 LinkedIn post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 27 reactions; 2 shares Twitter = 30 views; 1 like Facebook = 0 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7143884371123511297
	International Women's Day Celebration	The EFFECTIVE project highlighted some of its consortium partners (women) on its social networks, in March 2024, in order to celebrate them and, thus, also celebrate International Women's Day.	6 LinkedIn posts 6 Instagram posts 6 Facebook posts	LinkedIn = 23 reactions; 1 comment; 1 share (1 st post) + 40 reactions; 2 shares (2 nd post) + 40 reactions; 5 shares (3 rd post) + 33 reactions; 3 shares (4 th post) + 21 reactions (5 th post) + 26 reactions; 1 comment; 3 shares (6 th post). Instagram = 20 likes; 2 comments (1 st post) + 7 likes (2 nd post) + 7 likes (3 rd post) + 19 likes (4 th post) + 8 likes (5 th post) + 10 likes (6 th post). Facebook = 0 likes (1 st post) + 1 like (2 nd post) + 1 like (3 rd post) + 1 like (4 th post) + 0 likes (5 th post) + 0 likes (6 th post)	Link to LinkedIn post (example): https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171431133849534464
Benefits for Stakeholders Campaign	After an internal workshop organised by WP9 leaders, many EFFECTIVE benefits were identified for several	Benefits for Blue Economy Companies	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 13 views LinkedIn = 15 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 10 likes Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/06/12/benefits-that-the-effective-project-has-on-blue-economy-companies/
		Benefits for Marine Monitoring, Restoration,	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post	Website = 5 views LinkedIn = 23 reactions; 2 shares Instagram = 8 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/06/18/benefit

		stakeholder groups.	and Observation Specialists			s-that-the-effective-project-has-on-marine-monitoring-restoration-and-observation-specialists/
			Benefits for Scientists and Researchers	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post	Website = 11 views LinkedIn = 19 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 7 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/07/18/the-effective-project-benefiting-scientists-and-researchers/
			Benefits for MPA Managers with Data, Tools, and Expertise	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 4 views LinkedIn = 15 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 2 likes Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/08/08/the-effective-project-empowering-mpa-managers-with-data-tools-and-expertise/
			Benefits for Fisheries and aquaculture producers	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 4 views LinkedIn = 9 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 4 likes Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/08/14/effective-is-bringing-benefits-to-fisheries-and-aquaculture-producers/
			Benefits for Scuba Divers	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 15 views LinkedIn = 22 reactions; 1 comment; 1 share Instagram = 6 likes Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/08/20/the-effective-project-enriching-the-scuba-diving-experience-through-marine-conservation/
			Benefits for Port Managers	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Twitter post	Website = 7 views LinkedIn = 11 reactions Twitter = 15 views	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/09/03/the-effective-project-empowering-

					port-managers-in-the-transition-to-a-blue-economy/
		Benefits for Citizens	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 8 views LinkedIn = 11 reactions; 2 shares Instagram = 3 likes Twitter = 15 views Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/09/19/the-effective-project-empowering-local-communities-for-a-healthier-ocean/
		Benefits for Teachers and Students	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 6 views LinkedIn = 10 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 1 like Twitter = 18 views Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/10/02/the-effective-project-empowering-teachers-and-students-for-a-sustainable-future/
		Benefits for Regional authorities – policymakers	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 5 views LinkedIn = 6 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 2 likes Twitter = 23 views Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/10/10/the-effective-project-benefits-regional-authorities-policymakers/
		Benefits for Ecotourism entrepreneurs	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 5 views LinkedIn = 10 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 4 likes Twitter = 32 views Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/10/16/benefits-the-effective-project-brings-to-the-ecotourism-entrepreneurs/
		Benefits for Offshore Energy Companies	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 5 views LinkedIn = 10 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 3 likes Twitter = 115 views Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/10/29/the-effective-project-benefits-on-offshore-energy-companies/

		Campaign to gain Newsletter Subscribers	<p>3 LinkedIn posts 2 Twitter posts 3 Facebook posts 1 Instagram post</p>	<p>LinkedIn = 28 reactions; 1 share (1st post) + 25 reactions; 1 share (2nd post) + 14 reactions; 1 share (3rd post) Twitter = 128 views; 4 likes; 2 re-tweets (1st post) + 18 views (2nd post) Facebook = 0 likes (1st post) + 3 likes (2nd post) + 1 like (3rd post) Instagram = 4 likes</p>	<p>Link to LinkedIn post (example): https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7142833194965397504</p>
Events	Breaking the Surface Workshop	CMMI participated in the 15th Annual Breaking the Surface Workshop presenting the EFFECTIVE project to a diverse audience of experts, scientists, and industry leaders.	<p>1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post</p>	<p>Website = 26 views LinkedIn = 35 reactions; 4 shares Instagram = 5 likes Facebook = 5 likes; 2 shares</p>	<p>Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/11/30/cmami-shines-at-breaking-the-surface-workshop/</p>
	Smart City Expo World Congress/Tomorrow Blue Economy	Two EFFECTIVE partners participate in the side event of the Smart City Expo World Congress, held in Barcelona.	<p>1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post</p>	<p>Website = 3 views LinkedIn = 29 reactions; 4 shares Instagram = 11 likes Facebook = 0 likes</p>	<p>Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/12/13/effective-partners-at-the-smart-city-expo-world-congress/</p>
	Internal Citizen Science Workshop	On January 16, 2024, the EFFECTIVE consortium had a workshop about Citizen Science, led by the partner SPOTTERON.	<p>1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post</p>	<p>Website = 13 views LinkedIn = 35 reactions; 3 shares Instagram = 19 likes Twitter = 107 views; 4 likes; 1 re-tweet Facebook = 1 like</p>	<p>Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/01/24/exploring-the-possibilities-of-citizen-science-effective-citizen-science-workshop-2024/</p>
	1st Summit on Nature-Based	Organised by the EFFECTIVE project	<p>1 Website article 5 LinkedIn posts</p>	<p>Website = 32 views</p>	<p>Link to website article: https://effective-</p>

	Solutions for the Blue Economy	coordinator, Centro Tecnológico Naval y del Mar (CTN), in Murcia, Spain, in February 2028.	5 Instagram posts 2 Twitter posts 5 Facebook posts	LinkedIn = 27 reactions; 5 shares (1 st post) + 36 reactions; 3 shares (2 nd post) + 50 reactions; 7 shares (3 rd post) + 35 reactions; 3 shares (4 th post) + 58 reactions; 14 shares (5 th post) Instagram = 6 likes (1 st post) + 4 likes (2 nd post) + 11 likes (3 rd post) + 6 likes (4 th post) + 9 likes (5 th post) Twitter = 29 views; 3 likes (1 st post) + 32 views; 4 likes (2 nd post) Facebook = 0 likes (1 st post) + 2 likes; 1 share (2 nd post) + 2 likes (3 rd post) + 0 likes (4 th post) + 1 like (5 th post)	euproject.eu/2024/04/08/unveiling-insights-from-the-i-summit-on-nature-based-solutions-for-the-blue-economy/
	Horizon Europe Mission Ocean Work Programme	EFFECTIVE took center stage at the EU Research & Innovation session on effective marine management at the 2nd EU Blue Parks Community Workshop.	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Website = 13 views LinkedIn = 12 reactions; 2 shares Twitter = 26 views; 1 like Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/04/03/effective-project-showcased-at-eu-research-innovation-session-horizon-europe-mission-ocean-work-programme/
	EURESFO 2024	From June 26 to 28, the 11th edition of the European Urban Resilience Forum (EURESFO) brought together 450+ participants from 35 countries in Valencia,	1 Website article 3 LinkedIn posts 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 1 view LinkedIn = 2 reactions (1 st post) + 15 reactions; 1 comment; 2 shares (2 nd post) + 6 reactions; 1 share (3 rd post) Instagram = 4 likes Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/08/12/euresfo-2024-recap-advancing-urban-resilience/

		the European Green Capital for 2024.			
Newsletter	1 st Edition		1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 26 reactions; 2 shares Instagram = 4 likes Facebook = 1 like	Link to full Newsletter: https://mailchi.mp/eea83271563b/effective-project-newsletter-1
	2 nd Edition		1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 8 reactions Instagram = 2 likes Twitter = 19 views Facebook = 0 likes	Link to full Newsletter: https://lnkd.in/d6z_2myJ
Other	Articles with Partners' Collaboration	HCMR's Underwater Surveys in the Eastern Mediterranean	From July 8 to 15, HCMR undertook a significant endeavor, conducting underwater surveys in various regions, including Irakleio, Rethymno, Agios Nikolaos, Ierapetra, Chryssi Island, and Messara. These surveys were pivotal in assessing the ecological status of Posidonia oceanica meadows and rocky reefs, key components of the Mediterranean's rich marine ecosystem.	1 Website article	Website = 30 views Link to Website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/11/15/hcmrs-underwater-surveys-in-the-eastern-mediterranean/
		Ocean Ecostructures creates a biomaterial to	Ocean Ecostructures has developed a new technology to regenerate marine	1 Website article	Website = 21 views Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2023/11/15/ocean-ecostructures-creates-a-

		regenerate marine ecosystems	ecosystems, that uses a biomaterial made from byproducts, surpluses or waste that could not be reused.			biomaterial-to-regenerate-marine-ecosystems/
		Understanding Marine Protected Areas	Marine Protected Areas are designated regions in the ocean, seas, or other large water bodies where human activities are regulated to conserve the natural environment and ensure sustainable use of marine resources. These areas serve as sanctuaries for marine life, providing a haven for a diverse range of species, from the smallest microorganisms to the largest marine mammals.	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Collaborative Instagram Video 1 Facebook post	Website = 28 views LinkedIn = 52 reactions; 3 shares Instagram = 6 likes (1 st post) + 34 likes; 1 comment (2 nd post – collaborative) Facebook = 0 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/02/15/understanding-marine-protected-areas/
		Understanding the concept of a Digital Twin	A Digital Twin is essentially a digital replica of a physical entity, enabling users to access high-quality information, services, models, scenarios,	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 4 views LinkedIn = 22 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 3 likes Facebook = 2 likes	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/05/21/understanding-the-concept-of-a-digital-twin/

			forecasts, and visualizations.			
	Exploring Ecosystem-Based Management Systems (EBMS)	Ecosystem-Based Management Systems (EBMS) are a holistic approach to managing natural resources, focusing on the entire ecosystem, including human interactions. EBMS aim to maintain ecosystems in a healthy, productive, and resilient state by integrating ecological, social, and economic factors into decision-making processes.	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 13 views LinkedIn = 15 reactions Instagram = 6 likes Facebook = 1 like	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/05/29/exploring-ecosystem-based-management-systems-ebms/	
	Monitoring Expedition Pilot #1	The inaugural monitoring expedition of Pilot 1 by our partners Ocean Ecostructures, GPA Seabots, and the authorities of the Parc Natural del Montgrí, les Illes Medes i el Baix Ter marks a significant milestone in the EFFECTIVE project.	1 Website article 1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	Website = 18 views LinkedIn = 19 reactions; 2 shares Instagram = 11 likes Facebook = 1 like; 34 views of the video	Link to website article: https://effective-euproject.eu/2024/04/26/ocean-ecostructures-insights-from-monitoring-expedition-of-pilot-1/	

Content published only on EFFECTIVE social media channels	EFFECTIVE supports the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”	1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Twitter = 126 views; 5 likes; 2 re-tweets; 1 comment Facebook = 2 likes	Link to Twitter post: https://x.com/Effective2327/status/1696445153408426412
	One Ocean Foundation Report “Capturing the Blue Opportunity”	1 Twitter post	Twitter = 47 views; 4 likes	Link to Twitter post: https://x.com/Effective2327/status/1701285228483145900
	Introduction to Pilot #1	1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Instagram = 8 likes Twitter = 368 views; 8 likes; 5 re-tweets Facebook = 8 likes; 1 share	Link to Instagram post: https://www.instagram.com/p/CzBeKRAtWTU/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==
	Introduction to Pilot #2	1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	Instagram = 6 likes Twitter = 140 views; 4 likes; 1 re-tweets Facebook = 3 likes	Link to Instagram post: https://www.instagram.com/p/CzG8B89Nwn1/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==
	Introduction to Pilot #3	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 29 reactions; 4 shares Instagram = 12 likes Twitter = 97 views; 7 likes; 1 re-tweets Facebook = 2 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130482059961151488
	Iliad Digital Twins Of The Ocean as a Tool for Policymakers – The Case Of Fisheries" Workshop Promotion	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 14 reactions; 1 shares Instagram = 4 likes Twitter = 97 views; 1 like Facebook = 1 like	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7132356845997801472
	Fund raising by Ocean Ecostructures	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 31 reactions; 1 comment; 2 shares Instagram = 7 likes Facebook = 1 like; 1 share	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7141063004422389760

		Ocean Talks Interview	1 LinkedIn post	LinkedIn = 18 reactions; 1 share	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7180828803600957440
		REMEDIES Open Call Promotion	1 LinkedIn post	LinkedIn = 10 reactions	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7183395773496057856
		MPAs external article promotion	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 31 reactions; 3 shares Instagram = 4 likes Facebook = 0 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7184153101010931712
		MAF-WORLD Training School on 'Threats to Marine Animal Forests and Actions for Conservation/Restoration' event promotion	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Twitter post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 22 reactions; 4 shares Instagram = 10 likes Twitter = 55 views; 4 likes Facebook = 3 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7186642112816242689
		CMMI meeting with the Department of Fisheries and Marine Research (DFMR)	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post	LinkedIn = 35 reactions; 1 share Instagram = 10 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7191007841162293250
		Scientific Paper on Perspectives and Scenarios for Coastal Fisheries in a Social-Ecological Context: An Ecosystem Service Assessment Approach in the German Baltic Sea	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 18 reactions; 2 shares Instagram = 3 likes Facebook = 1 like	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7193544229019639809
		First sampling expedition of CMMI	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 29 reactions; 2 shares Instagram = 7 likes Facebook = 3 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7196088448754053122

		CMMI completed the initial phase of the Pilot study	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram post 1 Facebook post	LinkedIn = 27 reactions Instagram = 3 likes Facebook = 3 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201221346490519553
		Ocean Ecostructures monitoring within the framework of the project	1 LinkedIn post 1 Instagram collaborative post	LinkedIn = 45 reactions; 4 shares Instagram collaborative post = 57 likes	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7221417636876734464
		EFFECTIVE and CMMI on Euronews documentary series "Ocean"	1 LinkedIn post	LinkedIn = 27 reactions; 4 shares	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7234471391075401730
		iMermaid Open Call promotion	1 LinkedIn post	LinkedIn = 4 reactions	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7237019681780326400
		DALIA Open Call promotion	1 LinkedIn post	LinkedIn = 10 reactions; 1 share	Link to LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7238890875735408642

Table 2: Developed content and metrics from the main communication channels of the EFFECTIVE project (M1 - M17)

5.2 Social Media Followers

The EFFECTIVE project has experienced an exponential growth in social media followers up to M17, demonstrating the success of its digital outreach strategy. LinkedIn (currently with 689 followers) has emerged as the most impactful platform, attracting a significant and engaged audience. Instagram (144 followers by M17) and Twitter (53 followers) have also performed well, maintaining steady and consistent growth in followers. Conversely, the Facebook channel (with 37 followers) has proven less effective in drawing new followers, marking it as an area for potential improvement.

Figure 11: EFFECTIVE LinkedIn followers' growth until M17

Figure 12: Number of visits on EFFECTIVE LinkedIn page until M17

Figure 13: Engagement on EFFECTIVE LinkedIn until M17

5.3 Website Indicators

This section presents data on the number of visits and sessions recorded on the EFFECTIVE project website from its launch on November 28th, 2023, through M17 (October 2024). These metrics provide insights into the website's ability to attract and retain visitors, showcasing its importance as a central hub for information dissemination.

- The total number of unique users who have logged in the EFFECTIVE website: 1.337 users;
- The total number of active users in the EFFECTIVE website: 1.336 users;
- The number of pageviews on the EFFECTIVE website: 4,180 views.

Active users ?

1.3K

New users ?

1.3K

Figure 14: Number of Active Users in EFFECTIVE project Website

5.4 Newsletters Data

The EFFECTIVE project has successfully launched two newsletters, which have played a vital role in reaching and engaging its audience. This section presents the current number of subscribers, along with performance metrics for the newsletters, including the number of issues sent, click-through rates, and link engagement. These figures underline the effectiveness of the newsletters as a tool for disseminating project updates and fostering a deeper connection with stakeholders.

EFFECTIVE Newsletter #1

- Release Date: February 13, 2024 6:12 am
- Number of Recipients: 44

Figure 15: Mailchimp data on EFFECTIVE Newsletter #1

EFFECTIVE Newsletter #2

- Release Date: July 29, 2024 7:36 am
- Number of Recipients: 60

Figure 16: Mailchimp data on EFFECTIVE Newsletter #2

6. Conclusions

The communication and dissemination activities conducted by the EFFECTIVE project over the first 17 months have demonstrated significant progress in achieving the project's goals of raising awareness, fostering engagement, and promoting its core objectives among diverse audiences. Through targeted strategies and a multi-channel approach, the project successfully expanded its reach, strengthened stakeholder engagement, and positioned itself as a key initiative in Mediterranean marine protection and restoration.

Social media campaigns have driven exponential growth in audience engagement, with LinkedIn standing out as the most impactful platform. The project website has become a vital information hub, attracting a steady increase in visits and sessions since its launch. Newsletters have proven to be effective tools for direct engagement, providing regular updates and achieving notable subscriber and click-through rates. Additionally, the contributions of project partners have amplified visibility through posts, articles, interviews, and media appearances, further extending the project's outreach.

On the dissemination front, the publication of scientific articles, participation in technical workshops, and contributions to international conferences have effectively shared the project's findings with the research community. These efforts have enhanced the credibility and visibility of the EFFECTIVE project, supporting its mission to lead advancements in ecosystem-based management and Mediterranean marine conservation.

Moving forward, the project will continue to optimize its communication and dissemination strategies, leveraging the insights gained and addressing underperforming areas, such as Facebook engagement. The results thus far set a strong foundation for future activities, ensuring the EFFECTIVE project's long-lasting impact in both public and scientific spheres.